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Essential oils from Moroccan plants as promising ecofriendly tools to control toxic cyanobacteria blooms

Soukaina El Amrani Zerrifi^a, Ayoub Kasrati^{b,c}, El Mahdi Redouane^a, Zakaria Tazart^a, Fatima El Khalloufi^{a,d}, Abdelaziz Abbad^c, Brahim Oudra^a, Alexandre Campos^e and Vitor Vasconcelos^{e,f*}

^a Water, Biodiversity and Climate change laboratory. Phycology, Biotechnology and Environmental Toxicology Research Unit, Faculty of Sciences Semlalia Marrakech, Cadi Ayyad University, Av. Prince My Abdellah P.O. Box 2390, Marrakech 40000, Morocco. soukainaelamranizerrifi@gmail.com, redouane.elmahdii@gmail.com, zakaria.tazart@gmail.com, oudra@uca.ac.ma.

^b Private University of Marrakech, Morocco.

^c Biomolecule and Medicinal Chemistry Unit, Faculty of Science, Semlalia, Marrakech, Morocco. ayoub.kasrati@gmail.com, abbad.abdelaziz@gmail.com.

^d Polydisciplinary Faculty of Khouribga (FPK), Sultan Moulay Slimane University, Morocco. elkhalloufi.f@gmail.com.

^e CIIMAR, Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research, Terminal de Cruzeiros do Porto de Leixões, Av. General Norton de Matos, s/n, 4450-208 Matosinhos, Portugal. acampos@ciimar.up.pt.

^f Department of Biology, Faculty of Sciences, University of Porto, Rua do Campo Alegre, 4169-007 Porto, Portugal.

Corresponding author: vmvascon@fc.up.pt; Tel.: +351-223401817.

Abstract.

The use of natural compounds obtained from many plant resources are considered the most promising and eco-friendly alternative approach for controlling harmful algae in aquatic ecosystems. In this study, the anti-cyanobacterial activity of essential oils (EOs) extracted from seven Moroccan aromatic and medicinal plants against unicellular *Microcystis aeruginosa* has been evaluated. The chemical composition of EOs was analyzed by GC-MS, and a total of 55

constituents were identified accounting for 97.6 % to 100 % of the total oils. The potential algicidal activity was evaluated qualitatively by the application of the paper disk diffusion method in solid medium and quantitatively by the application of broth microdilution methods in liquid medium. The results of solid medium showed that *Chenopodium ambrosioides*, *Thymus broussonetii*, *Thymus maroccanus* and *Thymus satureioides* essential oils inhibited totally the growth of *Microcystis aeruginosa*. While, *Thymus Pallidus* essential oil exhibited the weakest activity. The growth of the tested cyanobacteria was completely inhibited during the 5-days test period in liquid media by *Thymus broussonetii*, *Thymus maroccanus* and *Thymus satureioides* essential oils, while the lowest inhibition rates was observed with *Thymus pallidus* essential oil. Regarding the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration values, it appears that *Thymus broussonetii* essential oil displayed the greatest potency, while the weakest effectiveness was achieved with *Thymus pallidus* essential oil. These findings provide a platform for the development of new ecofriendly and safer botanical materials, which may be used as effective alternative algicidal agents for controlling toxic cyanobacterial blooms.

Keywords: *Microcystis aeruginosa*; Anti-cyanobacterial activity; Essential oils; Moroccan; Bio-control.

1. Introduction

Harmful cyanobacterial blooms (Cyano HABs) represent one of the most conspicuous dangers to human health in drinking water resources and freshwater ecosystems (Harke et al., 2016). *Microcystis* species, as producer of diverse microcystins congeners, are among the most important worldwide freshwater bloom-forming cyanobacteria (Catherine et al., 2013). Multiple strategies have been applied to control or mitigate Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs). Nevertheless, the application of these strategies in the aquatic ecosystems is usually not effective owing to their low efficiency, nonselective toxicity to many organisms, and energy expenditure (Gao and Xie, 2011; Zerrifi et al., 2018). Accordingly, the search for an ecofriendly alternative approach based on the isolation of new bioactive molecules with potent effects against toxic cyanobacteria especially *M. aeruginosa* becomes an important issue in the field of water environment protection. The use of natural products is now emerging as one of the leading solution to prevent the development of microalgae (Li et al., 2016; Tazart et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018; Zerrif et al., 2018). The essential oils (EOs) are among natural plant products that are obtained from many aromatic and medicinal plants. These EOs have been reported to

possess a wide range of biological properties, including anti-cyanobacterial (Rivera et al., 2015). In fact, Najem et al. (2016) reviewed the anti-cyanobacterial activity of *Rosmarinus officinalis* EO on *M. aeruginosa* and *Chroococcus minor*. They found that the growth rates of both algae severely decreased as the time and the concentrations of the EO increased. Moreover, Wang et al. (2014) reported that EOs of two emergent plants *Typhalatifolia* and *Arundodonax* displayed significant growth inhibition against *M. aeruginosa*. Wang et al. (2015) investigated the effect of EOs excreted from six different submerged macrophytes, *Potamogeton cristatus*, *Potamogeton maackianus*, *Potamogeton lucens*, *Vallisneria spinulosa*, *Ceratophyllum demersum*, and *Hydrilla verticillata* on *M. aeruginosa*. The results showed that all tested macrophytes EOs inhibit the growth of *M. aeruginosa*. Moreover, Tellez et al. (2000) revealed that the growth of *Oscillatoria perornata* was strongly inhibited by *Callicarpa americana* EO. In addition, Ozaki et al. (2008) found that volatile organic compounds have lytic effects on toxic cyanobacteria.

Morocco is a Mediterranean country with diversified aromatic and medicinal flora characterized by numerous biological properties (Fennane and Tattou, 2012). However, the EOs of these plants are not investigated for their anti-cyanobacterial properties. The present study aims to valorize medicinal and aromatic plants of the Moroccan flora, in order to find novel anti-cyanobacterial plant based products. Thus, our work investigate for the first time the possible inhibitory effects of EOs extracted from seven Moroccan aromatic plants that are broadly known by their antimicrobial activities namely, *Chenopodium ambrosioides* L., *Thymus broussonetii*, Boiss., *Thymus maroccanus*, Ball, *Thymus pallidus* Batt., *Thymus satureioides* Coss, *Satureja calamintha* L. and *Mentha suaveolens* L. subsp. *timija* (Briq.) on the growth of *M. aeruginosa* a cyanobacteria species that commonly form HABs in Moroccan freshwaters.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Plant material and chemical composition of EOs

The aerial parts of *C. ambrosioides*, *T. broussonetii*, *T. maroccanus*, *T. pallidus*, *T. satureioides*, *S. calamintha* and *M. suaveolens* subsp. *timija* were harvested from different regions of Morocco (Table 1). Selection of plants was made based on ethnobotanical literature and traditional use in medicine and as antimicrobial agents (Bellakhder, 1997). The extraction and characterization of different EOs were applied using the methods described by Kasrati et al. (2014b).

Table 1. Locality, harvesting time and essential oil yield for the Moroccan aromatic plants studied.

Species	Species code	Harvesting place	Harvesting time	Voucher specimen	Latitude/Longitude	Oil Yield (% (v/ w))
<i>C. ambrosioides</i>	CA	What sidi Brahim	June 2014	CO036	N 31°30'/W 07°40'	0.86 ± 0.19
<i>T. broussonetii</i>	TB	Essaouira	February 2014	TB045	N 31°29'/W 09°33'	2.30± 0.14
<i>T. maroccanus</i>		Ait Ourir	June 2014	TM077	N 31°33'/W 07°40'	1.50 ± 0.13
<i>T. pallidus</i>		Ait Lkak	June 2014	TP057	N 31°17'/W 07°50'	1.99 ± 0.10
<i>T. satureioides</i>	TS	Ourika	June 2014	TS066	N 31°14'/W 07°41'	2.40 ± 0.03
<i>S. calamintha</i>	SC	Toufliht	June 2014	SC033	N 31°28'/W 07°26'	0.90 ± 0.05
<i>M. suaveolens</i> subsp. <i>timija</i>	MS	Toufiht	February 2014	MST09	N 31°28'/W 07°26'	0.63 ± 0.09

2.2. Screening for anti-cyanobacterial activity

2.2.1. Cyanobacteria strain

The descriptions of *M. aeruginosa*, isolation, separation into singles cell and maintenance procedure were determined according to the study of El Amrani Zerrifi et al., (2019).

2.2.2. Anti-cyanobacterial activity assays on solid media

The paper disc diffusion method was employed for the determination of the EOs anti-cyanobacterial activity (NCCLS., 1997a). A suspension of the tested cyanobacteria (inoculum prepared from a culture of 7 days) was spread on BG 13 medium consolidate with 0.4% of agarose (Shirai et al., 1989). Sterile filter paper discs (6 mm in diameter) were impregnated with 10 µL of each EOs and placed on the inoculated plates. The treated petri dishes were stored in a refrigerator at 4°C for at least 4 hours to allow diffusion of the bioactive substances. The DMSO and copper sulphate were employed as negative and positive control, respectively. All tests were performed in six-plicate to validate the findings statistically. Thereafter, the diameters of inhibition zones (ZI) were measured in millimeters after 7 days of incubation in a culture chamber under conditions of culture already mentioned above.

2.2.3. Anti-cyanobacterial activity assays on liquid media

In order to observe the cyanobacteria behavior vis-à-vis the essential oils (EOs), a test in liquid medium was carried out as described in the work of El Amrani Zerrifi et al., (2019). EOs prepared with DMSO (with concentration lower than 1% (v/v)) at a final concentration of five and 10 mg/L have been retained to be tested against *M. aeruginosa* cell culture.

2.2.4. Determination of the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was defined using the broth microdilution method according to the NCCLS guidelines M7-A4 (NCCLS., 1997b). All tests were performed in BG 13 media in triplicate. 100 μ L of tested cyanobacteria culture in exponential growth phase (3×10^6 cells/mL) were added to each well of 96-well plates. In order to get a serial dilution, stock solutions of EOs were diluted in DMSO (1%). The DMSO and copper sulphate were employed as negative and positive control, respectively. Subsequently, 100 μ L of each dilution was added to the tested culture to obtain final serial concentrations ranging from 0.023 to 50 mg/L. Plates were incubated under conditions of culture chamber already mentioned above and the incubation period has been determined on the results previously conducted on liquid medium. The cyanobacterial growth was indicated by the presence of a blue-green biomass. The MIC was defined as the lowest concentration of EOs that prevent visible growth of cyanobacteria, so no visible changes were detected in the broth medium after incubation period. To determine the MBC, 100 μ L of each well medium with no visible cyanobacterial growth was removed and inoculated in BG13. After 5 days of incubation period in culture chamber, the number of surviving *M. aeruginosa* cells has been determined. The MBC was determined as the lowest concentration of the EOs at which the incubated cyanobacteria was completely killed.

2.3. Statistical analysis

The experiments were repeated six times in solid medium ($n = 6$) and three times in liquid medium ($n = 3$). The Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests were used to determine data normality. The statistically significant differences between EOs experimental groups and the control were carried out by one-way and two-way ANOVA analysis. Differences with a *P*-value of < 0.001 were determined as statistically significant. As a post-test procedure, Tukey's honest significance test was used. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 21.0 statistical software.

3. Results

3.1. Chemical composition of EOs

The EO yields expressed in relation to dry weight of the plant materials are represented in Table 1. The highest and lowest yields were recorded by the EOs of *T. satureioides* ($2.4 \pm 0.03\%$) and *M. suaveolens* subsp. *timija* ($0.63 \pm 0.09\%$) respectively.

The qualitative and quantitative composition of the oils analyzed by GC-MS is shown in Table 2. In total 55 compounds were identified accounting for 97.6% to 100% of the total oil

composition. Oxygenated monoterpenes constituted the principal compound class in *M. suaveolens* subsp. *timija* (76.7%), *T. broussonetii* (64.5%), *T. maroccanus* (64.1%) and *T. satureioides* (61.9%) EOs, while *C. ambrosioides* (84.3%), *S. calamintha* (78.1%) and *T. pallidus* (58%) EOs were primarily composed by monoterpene hydrocarbons. The abundant compounds in *C. ambrosioides* EO were δ -3-carene (61.5%), p-cymene (14.7%), 1,2:3,4-diepoxy-p-menthane (8.1%) and 1,4-epoxy-p-menth-2-ene (6.2%). The EO extracted from *T. broussonetii* mainly consisted of carvacrol (43.4%), thymol (12.3%), γ -terpinene (8.9%) and borneol (8.5%). In the EO of *T. maroccanus*, the most predominant constituents were found to be carvacrol (64.1%), p-cymene (11.3%) and γ -terpinene (7.9%). *T. pallidus* EO was characterized by the dominance of γ -terpinene (29.6%) followed by thymol (26.8%) and p-cymene (18.9%). The EO isolated from the aerial parts of *T. satureioides* revealed the presence of carvacrol (25.3%), borneol (19.7%) and camphene (7.6%) as major compounds. The abundant constituents in *S. calamintha* EO were pulegone (56.6%), menthol (23.1%) and menthone (12.2%). Finally, the pulegone (23.4%), piperitenone oxide (22.6%), menthone (10.1%) and piperitone epoxide (9.1%) were the major constituents of *M. suaveolens* subsp. *timija* EO.

Table 2. Chemical composition of essential oils extracted from aerial parts of different Moroccan species studied (%).

Compound ^a	RI ^b	CA	TB	TM	TP	TS ^c	SC	MS
Tricyclene	925	- ^d	-	0.9	-	0.4	-	-
α -Thujene	928	-	1.2	-	1.4	0.9	-	-
Sabinene	975	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.2
α -Pinene	980	-	5.0	5.5	1.3	5.0	1.4	1.7
Octan-3-one	983	-	-	-	0.3	-	-	-
Myrcene	991	-	2.4	2.2	0.9	0.7	-	0.6
3-Octanol	993	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Camphene	998	-	3.4	-	2.2	7.6	-	0.2
α -Phellandrene	1007	0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
α -Terpinene	1018	-	1.3	1.8	2.7	1.0	-	-
β -Pinene	1028	-	0.7	-	-	0.8	1.1	1.7
Limonene	1030	0.6	0.9	1.6	0.7	1.3	4.2	3.8
cis-Ocimene	1031	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.8
δ -3-Carene	1033	61.5	-	-	-	0.5	-	-

p-Cymene	1035	14.7	5.2	11.3	18.9	6.6	-	-
γ -Terpinene	1059	1.2	8.9	7.9	29.6	5.0	-	-
Sabinene hydrate	1068	-	-	-	0.5	0.5	-	0.1
1,8-Cineole	1069	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.3
Linalool	1095	-	0.3	-	4.7	4.2	-	0.5
Octenylacetate	1110	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.3
Menthone	1155	-	-	-	-	-	12.2	10.1
Isomenthone	1164	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.9
Menthol	1166	-	-	-	-	-	23.1	-
Camphor	1168	-	-	-	-	0.3	-	-
cis-iso-Pulegone	1177	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.8
α -Terpineol	1192	-	-	-	-	3.3	-	0.3
cis-Dihydrocarvone	1196	-	-	-	-	0.3	-	-
Borneol	1198	-	8.5	-	5.4	19.7	-	-
Pulegone	1241	-	-	-	-	-	56.6	23.4
Carvacrolmethylether	1244	-	-	-	-	4.2	-	-
Terpinen-4-ol	1254	-	-	-	-	1.0	-	-
Piperitoneepoxide	1256	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.1
Menthylacetate	1272	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.7
Bornylacetate	1279	-	-	-	-	1.4	-	-
1,4-Epoxy-p-menth-2-ene	1281	6.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ascaridole	1294	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Thymol	1316	2.7	12.3	-	26.8	1.2	-	0.2
Carvacrol	1327	1.5	43.4	64.1	1.4	25.3	-	0.8
Piperitenone	1342	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.6
1,2:3,4-diepoxy-p-menthane	1348	8.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Piperitenoneoxide	1367	-	-	-	-	-	-	22.6
α -Copaene	1381	-	-	-	-	0.5	-	0.2
β -Elemene	1417	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.7
(E)-Caryophyllene	1425	-	-	2.5	2.9	5.4	-	2.2

Table 2. (Continued)

Compound ^a	RI ^b	Ca	Tb	Tm	Tp	Ts ^c	Sc	Ms
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Aromadendrene	1445	-	1.5	1.4	-	-	-	-
Viridiflorene	1501	-	3.7	0.9	-	-	-	-
α -Humulene	1460	-	-	-	-	0.2	-	0.4
Germacrene D	1486	-	0.3	-	-	0.4	-	3.2
Bicyclogermacrene	1502	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.2
γ -Cadinene	1519	-	-	-	-	0.4	-	0.4
δ -Cadinene	1528	-	0.3	-	-	0.8	-	0.3
Germacrene D-4-ol	1531	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.9
Spathulenol	1534	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.4
Caryophylleneoxide	1589	-	0.4	-	-	0.3	-	0.7
α -Cadinol	1645	-	-	-	-	0.3	-	0.7
Monoterpene hydrocarbons	84.3	29.0	31.2	58.0	29.3	78.1	10.0	
Oxygenated monoterpenes	13.3	64.5	64.1	38.8	61.9	19.5	76.7	
Sesquiterpene hydrocarbons	-	5.8	4.7	2.9	7.7	-	9.2	
Oxygenated sesquiterpenes	-	0.4	-	-	0.6	-	1.9	
Total (%)	97.6	99.7	100.0	99.4	99.5	97.6	97.8	

^a Compounds listed in order of elution.

^b RI (retention indices) measured relative to *n*-alkanes (C-9 to C-24) on a non polar DB-5 column.

^c Details concerning the codes of the species are given in Table 1.

^d Not detected.

3.2. Anti-cyanobacterial activity of EOs on solid media

The anti-cyanobacterial activity of the EOs was examined qualitatively by the application of the paper disk diffusion method. The measurement of the diameters of inhibition zones (ZI) has been realized after one week of incubation period. The Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests demonstrated that the diameters of ZI values were normally distributed. The results presented in Table 3 and Figure 1 showed that all investigated EOs displayed a variable degree of activity against *M. aeruginosa*. The most important activity was observed with the EOs of *C. ambrosioides*, *T. broussonetii*, *T. maroccanus* and *T. satureioides*, which have completely inhibited the growth of tested cyanobacteria (ZI = 90.00 \pm 0.00 mm). Notably, the growth inhibition of these oils is higher than the copper sulphate, used as positive control with ZI of 45.30 \pm 0.06 mm. Moderate activity was recorded with the EOs of *M. suaveolens* subsp. *timija* and *S. calamintha* (ZI of 29.30 \pm 0.06 mm and 24.30 \pm 0.06 mm, respectively). *T. pallidus* EO showed the lowest inhibitory effect against *M. aeruginosa* (ZI = 18.30 \pm 0.06 mm).

Table 3. Diameter of inhibition zones (ZI) of essential oils obtained from the aerial part of tested species.

Treatments	ZI (mm)
<i>C. ambrosioides</i>	90.00 ± 0.00 ^f
<i>T. broussonetii</i>	90.00 ± 0.00 ^f
<i>T. maroccanus</i>	90.00 ± 0.00 ^f
<i>T. pallidus</i>	18.34 ± 0.52 ^b
<i>T. satureioides</i>	90.00 ± 0.00 ^f
<i>S. calamintha</i>	24.34 ± 0.52 ^c
<i>M. suaveolens</i> subsp. <i>timija</i>	29.34 ± 0.52 ^d
Copper sulphate	45.34 ± 0.52 ^e
DMSO	06.00 ± 0.00 ^a

Each value representing mean ± SD of 6 replicates. For each sample, means with different letters are significantly different ($p < 0.001$).

Fig. 1. Anti-cyanobacterial activity of studied EOs against *M. aeruginosa* on solid media A). DMSO. B). *T. broussonetii*, *T. maroccanus*, *T. satureioides* and *C. ambrosioides*. C). *T. pallidus*. D). *S. calamintha*.

3.3. Evaluation of anti-cyanobacterial activity on liquid media

3.3.1. Inhibitory rates of EOs on tested cyanobacteria

The experimental results expressed in inhibition rates (IR%) of EOs on tested cyanobacteria are shown in Table 4 and Figure 2. The results were normally distributed, they showed that all EOs tested inhibited the growth of *M. aeruginosa* with marked and statistically significant way. At the first day of treatment, the most strong growth inhibition of the tested cyanobacteria was recorded by *T. broussonetii*, *T. maroccanus* and *T. satureioides* EOs (IR > 46%) at the first day of treatment. This inhibition increased gradually to value higher than 95% at the end of the experiment (Table 4). At a concentration of 10 mg/L of EOs, the growth of tested cyanobacteria was completely inhibited (IR = 100%). In fact, the culture medium of *M. aeruginosa* changed color from blue-green to blue and becomes colorless after the fourth day of treatment by *T. maroccanus* EO and by *T. broussonetii* and *T. satureioides* EOs at the end of experiment (Figure 2). Remarkably, the inhibition rate of these EOs are quite similar with that of copper sulphate, which showed an IR of 96.82%. *C. ambrosioides* and *T. pallidus* EOs showed the lowest inhibition rate with an inhibition rates lower than 19% at the beginning of the experiment. The effect of *C. ambrosioides* EO becomes important after the second day of treatment and the IR reached was greater than 78% in the last day of experiment. *M. suaveolens* subsp. *timija* EO has demonstrated a moderate activity throughout the experimental period.

Table 4. Inhibitory rates of the tested EOs, copper sulphate and DMSO on *M. aeruginosa* culture during 5 days of incubation period.

Treatments	Concentration (mg/L)	Time (days)					
		0	1	2	3	4	5
<i>C. ambrosioides</i>	5	0	12.45±1.54 ^{ab}	56.01±1.09 ^d	72.56±0.47 ^f	69.74±0.36 ^e	78.62±0.4 ^e
	10	0	18.4±1.49 ^{ab}	63.64±1.52 ^d	78.8±0.89 ^e	82.01±0.32 ^e	86.55±0.45 ^e
<i>T. broussonetii</i>	5	0	50.39±2.91 ^{cd}	87.99±0.38 ^g	92.41±0.4 ^{gh}	96.42±0.49 ^f	97.03±0.38 ^f
	10	0	65.7±3.58 ^e	89.25±0.82 ^f	93.51±0.4 ^f	96.57±0.49 ^f	100.00±0.00 ^g
<i>T. maroccanus</i>	5	0	46.63±2.11 ^{cd}	80.21±0.41 ^f	89.25±0.36 ^g	98.38±0.45 ^g	97.5±0.44 ^f
	10	0	61.55±2.28 ^e	84.07±0.96 ^e	90.18±0.14 ^f	100.00±0.00 ^h	100.00±0.00 ^g

<i>T. pallidus</i>	5	0	14.08±1.81 ^{ab}	40.67±0.47 ^c	30.98±0.47 ^b	28.77±0.47 ^b	25.09±0.68 ^c
	10	0	12.79±3.40 ^a	31.89±0.72 ^b	16.05±2.41 ^b	11.92±0.64 ^b	8.80±0.47 ^b
<i>T. satureioides</i>	5	0	46.02±4.18 ^{cd}	66.11±0.58 ^e	67.64±0.49 ^e	71.15±0.88 ^e	96.00±0.42 ^f
	10	0	64.01±0.68 ^c	89.44±0.54 ^f	99.42±0.06 ^g	99.70±0.01 ^h	100.00±0.00 ^g
<i>S. calamintha</i>	5	0	21.19±6.31 ^b	36.48±1.57 ^b	34.18±1.10 ^c	33.87±0.37 ^c	21.26±0.04 ^b
	10	0	22.40±2.71 ^b	50.77±1.32 ^c	39.18±1.25 ^c	40.03±0.14 ^c	16.96±0.42 ^c
<i>M. suaveolens</i> subsp. <i>timija</i>	5	0	37.31±4.90 ^c	63.25±0.80 ^e	63.35±0.8 ^d	66.06±0.17 ^d	36.4±0.24 ^d
	10	0	36.36±8.30 ^b	62.48±0.39 ^d	59.06±0.17 ^d	77.70±0.11 ^d	44.33±1.13 ^d
Copper sulphate	5	0	88.16±1.77 ^d	95.74±0.03 ^h	94.82±0.1 ^h	96.86±0.35 ^f	96.82±0.60 ^f
	10	0	90.08±0.3 ^d	97.05±0.46 ^g	97.25±0.76 ^g	98.03±0.86 ^g	98.56±0.37 ^f
DMSO		0	0.5±4.28 ^a	-1.18±1.55 ^a	0.7±0.22 ^a	-0.08±0.28 ^a	-0.02±1.53 ^a

Each value representing mean ± SD of 3 replicates. For each concentration, means with different letters are significantly different ($p < 0.001$).

Fig. 2. Inhibitory effect of different EOs against *M. aeruginosa* growing in liquid media at the last day of experiment A). *C. ambrosioides* at 5 mg/L. B). *T. broussonetii* at 10 mg/L. C). *T. broussonetii* at 5 mg/L. D). *T. broussonetii* at 10 mg/L. E). *T. maroccanus* at 5 mg/L. F). *T. maroccanus* at 10 mg/L. G). *T. pallidus* at 10 mg/L. H). Untreated culture.

3.3.2. Effect of EOs on growth rates of tested cyanobacteria

The growth rates of tested EOs at two concentrations (5 mg/L and 10 mg/L) against *M. aeruginosa* growth is shown as (μ) in Figure 3. The Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov

tests indicated that the growth rates values were normally distributed. The generation time of *M. aeruginosa* was about ~ 1.0 with the growth rates of 0.75 /day under standard culturing conditions. Copper sulphate used as positive control decreased significantly the growth of the tested cyanobacteria with μ values of 0.07 and 0.01 at 5 mg/L and 10 mg/L, respectively. The obtained data showed that *T. pallidus* EO at 10 mg/L had no significant effect on the growth rates of *M. aeruginosa*. The lowest effect on the growth rate was observed after treatment with *M. suaveolens* subsp. *timija*, *T. pallidus* and *S. calamintha* EOs (the μ values reached were 0.66, 0.69 and 0.70 at 5 mg/L, respectively and at of 10 mg/L the μ values recorded were 0.63, 0.73 and 0.71, respectively). *C. ambrosioides* EO showed a moderate effect on *M. aeruginosa* growth with μ equal to 0.44 at 5 mg/L and 0.35 at 10 mg/L. Moreover, the highest effect was revealed by *T. broussonetii*, *T. maroccanus* and *T. satureioides* EOs ($\mu < 0.11$ and $\mu < - 1.47$ at 5 mg/L and 10 mg/L, respectively).

Fig. 3. Effect of EOs, copper sulphate and DMSO on the growth rate of *M. aeruginosa*. Each value representing mean \pm SD of 3 replicates. For each concentration, means with different letters are significantly different ($p < 0.001$).

3.4. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)

The activity of essential oils extracted from aerial part of species studied against *M. aeruginosa* was demonstrated quantitatively by the application of broth microdilution methods. After 5 days of incubation, the observation of the MIC has been done and the results are

summarized in Table 5. In general, the MIC values confirmed the results obtained with the essay in solid media using paper disk diffusion method and the essay in liquid media. The positive control showed an important effectiveness (MIC = MBC = 3.12 mg/L). The greatest potency was achieved with EO obtained from *T. broussonetii* by MIC value of 0.047 mg/L and MBC value of 0.095 mg/L, followed by the EOs of *T. maroccanus* (MIC = MBC = 0.095 mg/L), *T. satureioides* (MIC = 0.095 mg/L and MBC = 0.19 mg/L). This activity was highest than that observed by the positive control (MIC = MBC = 3.12 mg/L). The weakest effectiveness was displayed by the EOs of *T. pallidus* (MIC = 12.5 mg/L and MBC = 25 mg/L), *S. calamintha* (MIC = MBC = 12.5 mg/L) and *M. suaveolens* subsp. *timija* (MIC = MBC = 12.5 mg/L). However, *C. Ambrosioides* oil had an intermediate activity (MIC = 3.12 mg/L and MBC = 12.5 mg/L).

Table 5. Anti-cyanobacterial activity of essential oils extracted from aerial part of species studied using broth microdilution method.

Treatments	MIC (mg/L)	MBC (mg/L)
<i>C. ambrosioides</i>	3.12	12.5
<i>T. broussonetii</i>	0.047	0.095
<i>T. maroccanus</i>	0.095	0.095
<i>T. pallidus</i>	12.5	25
<i>T. satureioides</i>	0.095	0.19
<i>S. calamintha</i>	12.5	12.5
<i>M. suaveolens</i> subsp. <i>timija</i>	12.5	12.5
Copper sulphate	3.12	3.12

MIC: minimum inhibitory concentration; MBC: minimum bactericidal concentration.

4. Discussion

The chemical analysis of the studied EOs revealed an important richness and variability of constituents. From the view of the volatile profile of *C. ambrosioides* EO, the studied chemotype is partially similar to those observed from Cameroon with a high content of δ -3-carene and

α -pinene (25.91% and 17.59%) (Langsi et al., 2018). While, p-cymene was the most dominated constituent in the EO extracted from *C. ambrosioides* of Egypt (39.2%) (Harraz et al., 2014), India (8.5%) (Kandpal et al., 2016) and Brazil (42.32%) (Degenhardt et al., 2016). Different composition was found by Santiago et al. (2016) which indicate that α -terpinene (40.73%) is the major constituent of *C. ambrosioides* EO. Carvacrol was found as a predominant component in the EOs of most *Thymus* species studied (*T. maroccanus*, *T. broussonetii* and *T. satureioides*). These results are in agreement with several studies previously published (Abrantes et al., 2006; Boskovic et al., 2015; Dias et al., 2017; El-jalel et al., 2018; Kasrati et al., 2014a; Khayari et al., 2016; Manconi et al., 2018). However, *T. pallidus* EO was characterized by the dominance of γ -terpinene and thymol. This finding is similar to those reported by Jamali et al. (2012). The data of this research demonstrated also that the pulegone, menthol and menthone were the major constituents of *S. calamintha* EO. These compounds are frequently found in other *S. calamintha* EO collected from Algeria and Corsica, but with some quantitative difference (Kerbouche et al., 2013; Labiod et al., 2015; Rossi et al., 2007). The abundant constituent in *M. suaveolens* subsp. *timija* EO were pulegone and piperitenone. This finding is qualitatively similar to that reported in previous works (Kasrati et al., 2015), but with some quantitative differences in the amount of the major compounds. In general, the quantitative and/or qualitative variation of volatile compounds observed in our EOs and those reported in previous works could be attributed to many factors including geographical location of the plant, plant age, period of harvesting and/or to the genetic variation within the species as postulated in many related works (Alcaraz-Meléndez et al., 2007; Viljoen et al., 2005).

Medicinal and aromatic plants are a reliable source of bioactive substances. Therefore, they could thence an ecofriendly alternative for controlling various environmental problems, which would also be less expensive (Spochacz and Chowa, 2018). Thence, we initiated to evaluate the anti-cyanobacterial activity of EOs isolated from seven medicinal and aromatic plants growing wild in Morocco. Initial screening in solid medium using the paper disk diffusion assay reveals that all tested EOs have a significant activity against the Gram-negative bacteria *M. aeruginosa*. The most important effect was recorded by the EOs of *C. ambrosioides*, *T. broussonetii*, *T. maroccanus* and *T. satureioides*. To our knowledge, this is the first study concerning the evaluation of anti-cyanobacterial activity of the studied EOs against *M. aeruginosa*. However, many reports have demonstrated the effect of these oils against several Gram-negative bacteria. The results of this study are in disagreement with those found by Alzubairi et al. (2017) who investigated the antibacterial activities of *C. ambrosioides* collected from Yemen. Their results show that the EO did not show any inhibition against tested Gram-

negative bacteria. Contrariwise, Harraz et al. (2014) observed that the EO isolated from aerial parts of *C. ambrosioides* show a strong antibacterial activity against Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*. Many recent studies have been confirmed the high antibacterial activity specially against Gram-negative bacteria of EOs extracted from aerial parts plants of genus *Thymus* (Demirci et al., 2018; Iseppi et al., 2018). After screening of three species of *Thymus* for their antibacterial activity, the EOs of *T. maroccanus*, *T. broussonetii* and *T. satureioides* showed significant growth inhibition of 32.17 ± 0.76 mm, 31.67 ± 1.53 mm and 22.33 ± 0.58 mm respectively, against Gram-negative bacteria *Salmonella* sp. (El Bouzidi et al., 2013). Sidali et al. (2017) reported that EO of the genus *Thymus* (*T. fontanesii*) demonstrate a potent antibacterial activity against Gram-negative *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* with diameter of inhibition zone equal to 11 ± 0.02 mm and 24 ± 0.5 mm, respectively. Although, in the present study *T. pallidus*, *S. calamintha* and *M. Suaveolens* subsp. *timija* EOs showed a moderate algicidal activity against *M. aeruginosa* compared with the other tested EOs on *M. aeruginosa*. This finding is in agreement with the observations of Tsimogiannis et al. (2017) who observed that *Satureja* genus EO recorded an moderate activity against Gram-negative bacteria *Salmonella enteritidis*, *E. coli* and *Salmonella typhimurium* (28 ± 0.6 mm 30 ± 0.6 mm and 32 ± 0.6 mm, respectively). Otherwise, weak inhibitory effects toward tested Gram-negative bacteria by the EO isolated from genus *Mentha* were observed (Brahmi et al., 2016).

In liquid medium, all tested EOs have a significant activity against the toxic cyanobacteria *M. aeruginosa*. Whereas, the most strong growth inhibition and the highest effect on growth rates were revealed by *T. broussonetii*, *T. maroccanus* and *T. satureioides* EOs. These results are in agreement with the observations of Habbadi et al. (2017) who demonstrated that the EO *T. vulgaris* showed highest activity antibacterial activity against the Gram-negative bacteria *Allorhizobium vitis* with a percentage inhibition of 41.6%. Tebaa et al. (2018) tested the effect of *T. satureioides* aqueous extract on the growth of *M. aeruginosa*. Their results show that the IRs reached was more than 88% after 8 days of treatment. In this work, characteristic color change in *M. aeruginosa* culture from blue- green to blue has been observed and at the end of treatment, the culture becomes colorless. This might be due to the presence of compound that induces cellular lysis. The same behavior was observed after treatment of unicellular *M. aeruginosa* by the volatile compound β -cyclocitral (Harada et al., 2009). Huang et al. (2002) suggested that the blue color formation of cyanobacteria might be due to acid stress. Recently, Windiasti et al. (2019) showed that the treatment with carvacrol induce cell deformation and cause damage to the cell membrane of Gram-negative bacteria *Campylobacter jejuni*. Also, this compound is considered as biocidal, resulting a variety of molecular mechanisms on bacteria

cells, including disrupting cell membrane, depleting intracellular ATP, inducing reactive oxygen species, inhibiting efflux pumps (Zhang et al., 2018). Therefore, in this study the cellular lysis of *M. aeruginosa* can be explained by the presence of carvacrol, the major constituent of tested EOs extracted from *T. broussonetii*, *T. maroccanus* and *T. satureioides*. Concerning *C. ambrosioides* EO, the anti-cyanobacterial activity observed is presumably associated with the high percentage of δ -3-carene as suggested (Cosentino et al., 2003). While piperitenone oxide and pulegone could contribute to the moderate anti-cyanobacterial of *M. suaveolens* subsp. *timija* EO (Božović et al., 2015; Gulluce et al., 2007).

5. Conclusion

For the first time, the evaluation of anti-cyanobacterial activity of seven Moroccan plant essential oils have been realized in this work. The obtained data showed that all studied EOs has presented an interesting activity against the toxic cyanobacteria *M. aeruginosa* in a concentration-dependent way. The greatest effectiveness was recorded with *T. broussonetii* EO while the weakest potency rates was achieved with *T. pallidus* EO. Therefore, Effective major components contained in the studied EOs will be further investigated to better comprehend the potential inhibitory effect of these EOs. In addition, the search for the stability of active major components and their potential synergistic interactions in macrocosms and environmental conditions is a crucial step before suggesting them as alternative anti-cyanobacterial natural agents for HABs controlling.

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